

TARIXIMSAN, TAQDIRIMSAN ONA TILIM
YOU ARE HISTORY, YOU ARE DESTINY, MY MOTHER LANGUAGE

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ona tili insoniyat uchun qanchalar muhimligi, millatning ruhi ekanligi, o'zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berilgani hamda ona tilimizning tarixi, rivojlanish jarayonlari va uning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ona tili, o'zbek tili tarixi, davlat tili, globallashtirish, til bayrami, rivojlanish, sayqal topishi, ijtimoiy - siyosiy, milliy til.

Abstract: In this article, the importance of the mother tongue for humanity, the soul of the nation, the fact that the Uzbek language has been given the status of the state language, and the history, development processes of our mother tongue and its importance today are highlighted.

Key words: mother tongue, history of the Uzbek language, state language, globalization, language holiday, development, development, socio-political, national language.

KIRISH

Har bir til tarixiy taraqqiyot bilan boyib boradi. Bu jarayon tilning ichki imkoniyatlari asosida va boshqa tillardan so'zlarni o'zlashtirish orqali amalga oshadi. Mamlakatlar va xalqlar o'rtasidagi ijtimoiy-siyosiy, iqtisodiy-madaniy munosabatlarning mustahkamlanishi natijasida, ayniqsa, qo'shni xalqlarning o'zaro munosabati natijasida bir tildan ikkinchi tilga yangi tushunchalarni ifodalovchi so'zlar qabul qilinadi. Bugungi globallashtirish davrida bu jarayon yanada kuchaydi. Turk tilining, jumladan, o'zbek tilining boyligini Mahmud Koshg'ariy, Yusuf Xos Hojib, Alisher Navoiy, Mirzo Bobur kabi bobolarimiz isbotlagan. Rus, ukrain, fors tillari turkiy tillardan muhim so'zlarni qabul qilgan. Yevropa tillari ham bundan ma'lum darajada chetda qolmagan. Tilimizda shunday so'zlar borki, ularni ko'pchilik boshqa tillardan kirib kelgan deb o'ylaydi. Darhaqiqat, o'zimizniki bo'lgan bunday "dunyoviy" so'zlar biroz o'zgarish bilan bizga qaytdi.

INTRODUCTION

Every language is enriched by historical development. This process takes place on the basis of the internal capabilities of the language and by acquiring words from other languages. As a result of the strengthening of social-political, economic-cultural relations between countries and peoples, especially as a result of the interaction of neighboring peoples, words expressing new concepts from one language to another are accepted. In today's era of globalization, this process has intensified. The richness of the Turkish language, including the Uzbek language, was proven by our great-grandfathers like Mahmud Koshgari, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Alisher Navoi, Mirzo Babur. Russian, Ukrainian, and Farsi-speaking languages have adopted important words from Turkic languages. European languages have not been spared from this to a certain extent. There are words in our language that many people think have come from other languages. In fact, such "worldly" words, which are our own, have returned to us with a slight change.

MATERIALLAR VA USULLAR

“O‘zbek tili kambag‘al emas, lekin o‘zbek tilini bechora deganlarning o‘zlari bechoralar, o‘z bilimsizliklarini o‘zbek tiliga o‘tkazmasinlar”, deydi ma‘rifatparvar bobomiz Abdulla Qodiriy.

Tarixdan ma‘lumki, ona tilimiz bir necha ming yillar davomida o‘z ahamiyatini yo‘qotmagan. O‘zbek tilining eng muhim jihati shundaki, u shunchalik shirali, har bir quloqqa yoqimli, eshitgan kishi nafas oladi. Ona tilimiz, shoir Mirtemir aytganidek, yoshligimizdan qalbimizga singib ketgan. Onalarimiz aytgan ertaklar va bobo-buvilarimizdan eshitgan ertaklar, ertaklar, rivoyat va matallar orqali qalbimiz tubiga kirib bordi, o‘z navbatida ona tilimizga, ona yurtimizga muhabbat tuyg‘ularini singdirdi. O‘zbekistonning har bir fuqarosi o‘z ona tilida so‘zlashadi. sevadi, hurmat qiladi va hurmat qiladi. Chunki har qanday xalq qanday yashayotgani, rivojlanayotgani yoki aksincha, orqada qolib, qashshoqlashib borayotganini faqat shu til orqali bilib olishimiz mumkin. Shuning uchun ham “Til – millat ko‘zguvidir”[1], deb bejiz aytishmagan.

1989-yil 21-oktabr.“Davlat tili to‘g‘risida”gi qonun qabul qilindi, o‘zbek tiliga Davlat tili maqomi berildi. Xalqimizning muqaddas qadriyatlaridan biri bo‘lgan ona tilimiz o‘zining huquqiy maqomiga ega bo‘ldi va himoyalandi. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasida davlat tilining maqomi huquqiy jihatdan mustahkamlandi. Shu tariqa o‘zbek tiliga yurtimiz bayrog‘i, gerbi, madhiyasi kabi qonun bilan qo‘riqlanadigan muqaddas davlat ramzlari bilan birga hurmat va ehtirom

ham qozonildi. Keyingi yillarda davlat tilining ijtimoiy hayotdagi mavqeini yanada mustahkamlash maqsadida qator ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Xususan, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 21-oktabrdagi qarori bilan O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining tarkibiy bo‘linmasi hisoblangan Davlat tilini rivojlantirish boshqarmasi tashkil etildi. Bundan ko‘zlangan maqsad davlat tilini rivojlantirish, davlat tilining qo‘llanilishi bilan bog‘liq muammolarni aniqlash va bartaraf etish bo‘yicha takliflar tayyorlash, o‘zbek tilining yozma matniga oid me‘yor va qoidalarni ishlab chiqishdan iborat. Milliy tilimizga, ona tilimizga e'tibor nafaqat bugungi kun, balki tarixning barcha davrlarida ham dolzarb bo'lib qoldi[2]. Shu o‘rinda bobolarimizning quyidagi hikmatli so‘zlarini eslaylik: “Til va adabiyot har bir xalqning dunyoda borligini ko‘rsatadigan asosiy hayotidir. Milliy tilni yo‘qotish – millatning ruhini yo‘qotishdir” (M. Behbudiy). E'tibor beryapsizmi, milliy tilni yo'qotish millat tilini yo'qotish bilan taqqoslanadi. Darhaqiqat, tilning ahamiyati, mavjudligi har qanday davlat va millat taraqqiyotini belgilab berishi shubhasiz. Ayniqsa, bugungi globallashuv davrida, dunyo xalqlarining turmush tarzi umumiy bo‘lib qolgan bir paytda yuqoridagi so‘zlarning ahamiyati ikki barobar ortib bormoqda.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

"The Uzbek language is not poor, but those who call the Uzbek language poor are themselves poor. They should not transfer their ignorance to the Uzbek language," said our enlightened grandfather Abdulla Qadiri.

History shows that our mother tongue has not lost its importance for several thousand years. The most important aspect of the Uzbek language is that it is so juicy, it is pleasant to every ear, and the person who hears it will gasp. Our native language, as the poet Mirtemir said, has been ingrained in our hearts since we were young. Through the tales told by our mothers and the tales, stories, narratives and parables we heard from our grandparents, our hearts penetrated to the depths, and in turn, they instilled love for our mother tongue and our motherland. Every citizen of Uzbekistan speaks his mother tongue. loves, respects and honors him. Because it is only through this language that we can know how any nation is living, developing, or, on the contrary, lagging behind and getting poorer. That is why it is not for nothing that they say: "Language is the mirror of the nation." [1]

October 21, 1989. The Law "On the State Language" was adopted, and the Uzbek language was given the status of the State Language. Our mother tongue, which is one of the sacred values of our people, got its legal status and protection. In the

Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the status of the State language has been legally strengthened. In this way, the Uzbek language has received honor and respect, as well as sacred state symbols protected by law, such as the flag, emblem, and anthem of our country. In recent years, a number of works are being carried out in order to further strengthen the position of the state language in social life. In particular, by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 21, 2019, the Department of State Language Development, which is considered a structural unit of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, was established. The purpose of this is to develop the state language, to prepare proposals for identifying and eliminating problems related to the use of the state language, to develop norms and rules for the written text of the Uzbek language. Attention to our national language, our mother tongue, has become relevant not only today, but also in all periods of history[2]. At this point, let's remember the following wise words of our grandfathers: "Language and literature are the main life of every nation that shows its presence in the world. To lose the national language is to lose the spirit of the nation" (M. Behbudi). Do you notice that losing the national language is compared to losing the language of the nation. In fact, there is no doubt that the importance of language, its existence determines the development of any country and nation. Especially in today's globalization era, when the lifestyle of the peoples of the world has become common, the significance of the above words increases twice.

TADQIQOT VA MUHOKAZA

Til millat ko'zgusi, ma'naviyat ko'zgidir. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Birinchi Prezidenti Islom Abdug'aniyevich Karimov ona tilimiz haqida bejiz gapirgan edi: "Barcha ezgu fazilatlar inson qalbiga, eng avvalo, ona tilining betakror jozibasi bilan singib ketgan." Ona tili – bu millatning ruhi". Tilini yo'qotgan har qanday xalq o'zligidan ajralishi muqarrar. Tilimiz haqida yozuvchi va shoirlarimiz ko'plab hikmatli so'zlarni aytib, unga turlicha ta'rif berganlar[3].

Ta'lim tizimida minglab tillardan foydalanish imkoniyati yo'q. Internetda ishlatib bo'lmaydigan tillar haqida gapirma ham bo'ladi. Chunki yangi texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi tufayli ayrim xalqlar o'z tili o'rniga zamonaviy tillardan foydalanishga majbur bo'lmoqda. Bugungi kunda Internet tilining 81% ingliz tilidir. To'g'ri, tillar o'tmishda paydo bo'lgan, muammoga duch kelgan va ma'lum vaqtdan keyin yo'q bo'lib ketgan. Ammo tillarning hozirgidek tez yo'q bo'lib ketishi tarixda kuzatilmagan. Yo'qolib borayotgan tillarni asrab-avaylashga qaratilgan sa'y-harakatlarning asosiy maqsadi madaniyatlar va tillar xilma-xilligini ta'minlashdan

iborat. Chunki aynan til tufayli xalqlar va elatlarning madaniyati, an'analari saqlanib qolmoqda, sayyoramizda yashayotgan xalqlarning o'tmishi, madaniyati e'zozlanadi.

Tilshunoslarning ta'kidlashicha, yo'qolib borayotgan tillarni saqlab qolish imkoniyatlari hali ham boy bermagan. Tillarni saqlab qolish uchun BMT ekspertlarining fikricha, ta'lim tizimida ushbu tillardan keng foydalanishni yo'lga qo'yish zarur. Til millatning ma'naviy boyligidir. Til nafaqat muammolar quroli, balki xalqning madaniyati, urf-odatlar, turmush tarzi, tarixidir. Turli xalqlar tillariga hurmat, o'z navbatida, o'zaro tushunish va muloqot qilish imkoniyatlarini yaratadi. Tillarni saqlab qolish uchun bu tillarni qo'llab-quvvatlash kerak. Insoniyat u yoki bu millatga mansubligi bilan faxrlanadi[4].

Inson uchun ona tili qanchalik muqaddas bo'lsa, ona Vatan, ota-ona, oila ham shunday muqaddasdir. Hatto chaqaloq ham ona tili orqali dunyoni tushunadi. Darhaqiqat, davlat tilini bilish va undan amalda to'liq foydalana olish, "Davlat tili to'g'risida"gi qonunga rioya qilish, uni hayotga tatbiq etish, uni qadrlash yuksak ma'naviyat belgisidir, degan g'oya "Davlat tili" tushunchasining o'zagini tashkil etadi. davlat tili. yetarli. Qonunga ko'ra, o'zbek tilini bilmagan fuqarolar bepul o'qitilishi va o'qitilishi mumkin. O'zbek tili (o'zbek yoki turkiy o'zbek) — oltoy tillari oilasining turkiy oilasiga mansub til. Bu til O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasiga muvofiq davlat tili hisoblanadi. 1989-yil 21-oktabrda "Davlat tili to'g'risida"gi qonun qabul qilingan. 1995-yil 21-dekabrda yangilangan. O'zbek adabiy tili tarixi quyidagi davrlarni o'z ichiga oladi: miloddan avvalgi 10-asr. Bu davr tili fanda qadimgi turkiy til sifatida tanilgan. Bu tilda qadimiy xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalari, O'rxun-Enasoy yodgorliklari (VI-VII asrlar) yaratilgan. 11—14-asrlarda qo'llanilgan til eski turk tili deb ataladi. Mahmud Koshg'ariyning "Devonulug'atit-turk" ("Turkiy tillar kutubxonasi"), Yusuf Xos Hojibning "Qutadg'u bilig" ("Baxtga yetaklovchi bilim"), Ahmad Yugnakiyning "Hibatul-haqoyiq" ("Haqiqatlar – armug") oni), Xorazmiyning "Muhabbatnoma"si, Rabg'uziyning "Qissai Rabg'uziy"i shu tilda yozilgan. 19-asrning 15—2-yarmigacha qo'llanilgan til eski o'zbek adabiy tili deb atalgan. Atoyiy, Sakkokiy, Sayfiy asarlari. Bu tilda Saroy, Lutfiy, Alisher Navoiy, Bobur, Mashrab, Turdi, Maxmur, Gulxaniy, Muqimiy, Furqat, Zavqiy va boshqa ko'plab ijodkorlar yaratilgan[5].

19-asrning 2-yarmidan hozirgi kungacha qo'llanilgan til hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili deb ataladi. "Turkiston viloyati gazetasi" nashr etilgandan (1870 yildan) to hozirgacha yaratilgan barcha asarlar hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili namunalari. Bundan 27 yil avval o'zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berilgan edi. Bu o'z davrida tom ma'noda

global voqea edi. Chunki Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Al Xorazmiy, Al Farg‘oniy, Alisher Navoiy, Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulug‘bek, Bobur Mirzo kabi buyuk siymolarni yetishtirgan milliy til yo‘qolib ketish arafasida edi. Mustaqillik sari ilk qadamlar qo‘yilayotgan bir paytda o‘zbek tiliga davlat maqomi berish masalasi Prezidentimiz tomonidan kun tartibiga qo‘yilgan va bu ishlar amalga oshirilgan edi. 1989-yil 21-oktabrda ona tilimiz o‘zbek tiliga davlat tili maqomi berildi[6]. Bu mamlakatimiz va yurtdoshlarimiz hayotida unutilmas, tarixiy voqea bo‘ldi. Agar o‘shanda til to‘g‘risidagi qonun qabul qilinmaganida, o‘zbek tili tarix sahifalariga kirgan bo‘larmidi?!

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

Language is a mirror of the nation, a reflection of spirituality. The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov, spoke of our mother tongue for nothing: "All the good qualities are engrained in the human heart, first of all, with the unique charm of the mother tongue. "Mother language is the soul of the nation." It is inevitable that any nation that loses its language will be separated from its identity. Our writers and poets have said many wise words about our language and defined it in different ways[3].

There is no opportunity to use thousands of languages in the educational system. Not to mention the languages that cannot be used on the Internet. Because due to the development of new technologies, some nations are forced to use modern languages instead of their own. Today, 81% of the Internet language is English. It is true that languages have appeared in the past, were in trouble, and disappeared after a certain time. But such a rapid disappearance of languages as now has not been observed in history. The main goal of efforts to preserve endangered languages is to ensure the diversity of cultures and languages. Because it is thanks to the language that the culture and traditions of peoples and nations are preserved, and the past and culture of the peoples living on our planet are respected.

Linguists say that the opportunities to save endangered languages are not lost yet. In order to preserve the languages, according to the UN experts, it is necessary to establish a wide use of these languages in the education system. Language is the spiritual wealth of the nation. Language is not only a tool for problems, but also a people's culture, traditions, lifestyle, and history. Respect for the languages of different nations, in turn, creates opportunities for mutual understanding and communication. In order to preserve languages, it is necessary to support these

languages. It is because of the language that humanity is proud of belonging to one or another nation[4].

Mother tongue is as sacred as motherland, parents, and family are for a person. Even a baby understands the world through his mother tongue. In fact, the idea that knowing the state language and being able to fully use it in practice, observing the Law "On the State Language", implementing it, and appreciating it is a sign of high spirituality forms the core of the concept of the state language. is enough. According to the law, citizens who do not know the Uzbek language can be taught and taught free of charge. The Uzbek language (Uzbek or Turkic Uzbek) is a language belonging to the Turkic family of the Altaic language family. This language is the state language according to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Law on the State Language was adopted on October 21, 1989. Updated on December 21, 1995. The history of the Uzbek literary language includes the following periods: from BC to the 10th century. The language of this period is known as the ancient Turkic language in science. Samples of ancient folklore, monuments of Orhun-Enasoy (VI-VII centuries) were created in this language. The language used in the 11th-14th centuries is called the old Turkish language. Mahmud Kashgari's "Devonu-lug'atit-turk" ("The Library of Turkish Languages"), Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Kutadgu Bilig" ("Knowledge that Leads to Happiness"), Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibatul Haqayiq" ("Truths are Armug "oni"), Khorezmi's "Muhabbatnama" and Rabguzi's "Qissai Rabguzi" were written in this language. The language used from the 15th to the second half of the 19th century was called the old Uzbek literary language. The works of Atoyi, Sakkoki, Saifi Saraoi, Lutfi, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Mashrab, Turdi, Makhmur, Gulkhani, Muqimi, Furqat, Zavqi and many other artists were created in this language[5].

The language used from the second half of the 19th century to the present is called the modern Uzbek literary language. All the works created since the publication of "Turkestan Region Gazette" (from 1870) until now are examples of the modern Uzbek literary language. 27 years ago, the Uzbek language was given the status of the state language. It was literally a global event in its time. Because the national language, which produced such great figures as Beruni, Ibn Sina, Al Khorazmi, Al Farghani, Alisher Navoi, Amir Temur, Mirza Ulugbek, Babur Mirza, was on the verge of disappearing. At the time when the first steps towards independence were being taken, the issue of granting state status to the Uzbek language was put on the agenda by our president, and this work was carried out. On October 21, 1989, our mother tongue, Uzbek, was given the status of a state language[6]. This has become an

unforgettable, historical event in the life of our country and compatriots. If the law on language had not been adopted then, would the Uzbek language have entered the pages of history?!

XULOSA

Zero, til millat qiyofasining bir qismidir. Dunyodagi barcha xalqlarning o‘z milliy rasmiy tili bor deb ayta olmaymiz. Chunki bu xalqning milliy mustaqilligi bilan bog‘liq. Mutaxassislarning fikricha, har ikki haftada bitta til yo‘qolib bormoqda. YuNESKO vakillarining ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, bir vaqtlar odamlar so‘zlashadigan tillar soni 7-8 mingga yetgan bo‘lsa, bugungi kunda sayyoramizda 6000 ta til mavjud. lib, ularning 90 foizi yo‘q bo‘lib ketish arafasida. Bular asosan sivilizatsiya tufayli o‘z madaniyatini yo‘qotayotgan oz sonli xalqlarning tillaridir. Bu tillarda gapiradigan odamlarning ba‘zilari yozuvga ega, boshqalari esa yo‘q. Misol uchun, Afrika tillarida so‘zlashuvchi aholining 80% hali ham o‘z yozuviga ega emas. Zero, har bir inson bilishi kerak bo‘lgan jihat shuki, ona tili nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki Vatanga muhabbat, milliy g‘urur, ajdodlarga hurmat, demak, avlodlarimizga hurmat timsoli hamdir. O‘z tilini saqlagan xalq o‘zligini saqlaydi.

CONCLUSION

After all, language is a part of the image of a nation. We cannot say that all peoples of the world have their own national official language. Because it is related to the national independence of the people. According to experts, one language is disappearing every two weeks. According to representatives of UNESCO, the number of languages spoken by people once reached 7,000 to 8,000, but today there are 6,000 languages on our planet. lib, 90 percent of them are on the verge of extinction. These are mainly the languages of a small number of nations that are losing their culture due to civilization. Some of the people who speak these languages have writing, while others do not. For example, 80% of the population speaking African languages still do not have their own writing. After all, the point that everyone should know is that the mother tongue is not just a means of communication, but also a symbol of love for the Motherland, national pride, respect for ancestors, and, therefore, honor for our descendants. A nation that preserves its language preserves its identity.

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